

Conservation of Momentum in terms of Probability, Space and Time

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Space and time are sometimes placed on the same footing so to speak. Newton's second law: $dp/dt = \text{Force}$ is written in terms of time, but it may also be written in terms of x , i.e. $dp/dx \cdot dx/dt = \text{Force}$. For a nonzero force this requires extra information, but for a zero force it does not because $dp/dt = dp(x)/dx = 0$. Even in the constant p case, however, we argue that time and space are not treated in the same manner. For a situation in which two p 's collide at x with conservation of momentum (i.e. F and $-F$ equalling 0), one has p_1+p_2 (vectors) at t_1 and p_3+p_4 at t_2 , but both p_1+p_2 and p_3+p_4 exist at the same x . There is no before and after for x , yet one must somehow distinguish between a before and after.

If one thinks in terms of probabilities, one may say that there is a probability to have a p_1 at x , but one may note that there is no time here. If one had time, one would follow the particle deterministically and there would be no probability. Thus, $P(p_1, x)$ is the probability to have p_1 at x . If one has $P(p_2, x)$ and one writes $P(p_1, x)P(p_2, x)$ one assumes the same time for p_1 and p_2 to be at x , but this is the same as having p_1+p_2 at x so: $P(p_1, x)P(p_2, x) = P(p_1+p_2, x)$. If one were to argue that x does not matter, this leads to a power law for $P(p_1)$, i.e. $\exp(\text{constant } p_1)$. (one dimension) Now if a reaction occurs, one has p_1+p_2 and p_3+p_4 at the same x , but p_1+p_2 exist at one time and p_3+p_4 at another. As noted above, one must distinguish. We argue that one distinguishes by noting that $p_1+p_2=p_3+p_4$ (conservation of momentum-vectors), so $(p_1+p_2)-(p_3+p_4)=0$. In other words, a minus sign may be used to distinguish time. This is like using a time reversed solution.

The problem now is that $P(-p_3-p_4) P(p_1+p_2)$ should be 0, but it cannot be due to the power law solution. Thus, one cannot use probability at a point to argue conservation of momentum.

Formally, however, a reaction may take place at any x and so the power law $\exp(p_1)$ may not be the probability form with x integrated out. In other words, one may argue that the full expression is: $0 = \text{Sum over } x \ P(-p_3-p_4, x) P(p_1+p_2, x)$. This then leads to $\exp(ipx)$ (not growing or shrinking indefinitely) as $P(p, x)$. The main point is that $P(p, x)$ is a function of two variables and so should be associated with continuity of both $\exp(ipx)$ as a probability in space and average momentum density: $p \exp(ipx)$. Thus, a probabilistic mechanism needed to ensure momentum conservation, i.e. $\exp(ipx)$, automatically involves two variables, x, p and two sets of continuity equations if there is symmetry at some x_0 .

At this point, one may ask: What is the use of $\exp(ipx)$? This form was developed using the notion of spatial invariance. A reaction leads to a change in p and occurs at point x . For p_1+p_2 conserved, there is total conservation of momentum and so it is like having $\exp(i p_{\text{total}} x)$. What if one has a single particle and its p changes? This change must occur at some x . (This x point is invariant, but there is symmetry breaking in x .) How does one deal with the symmetry breaking in x ? If no work is done, then even though p changes, energy remains the same and there is no symmetry breaking in time. In one dimension, one may have $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$ in the x region to the left of the interaction point x_0 (i.e. a solution and its time reversed result) and $\exp(ip_2 x)$ to the right. If $\exp(ipx)$ is a probability function it should be continuous at x_0 . A main feature of probability, however, is to compute average values and so pave using $\exp(ipx)$ should be the first average of consequence and so it too should be continuous at x_0 . These two

conditions, with x symmetry breaking and p value breaking still lead to before and after time results, but because one is dealing with a probability picture, there are probabilities for these.

Momentum Conservation and Probabilistic Viewpoint

As is well known, conservation of momentum follows from Newtonian mechanics using $dp_1/dt = F$ and $dp_2/dt = -F$ so $d/dt (p_1+p_2) = 0$. This interaction may occur at any x and time and one only knows p_1 and p_2 at that x and t . Thus, conservation of momentum follows from Newton's second law and it holds for any x and t .

Consider now a probabilistic viewpoint which considers finding a momentum p at x at some t which is not specified. For an interaction to occur, which may be a function of space only, e.g. $F(x) = -dV/dx$, one should have:

$$P(p_1, x)P(p_2, x) = P(p_1+p_2, x) \quad ((1a)) \quad \text{where } p_1 \text{ and } p_2 \text{ are vectors}$$

Time is not specified, but it is understood that p_1 and p_2 exist at x at the same time. In the Newtonian view, one would not even specify x because all x points are the same. This suggests a power law probability for one dimension, i.e.

$$P(p) = \exp(\text{constant } p) \quad ((1b))$$

In the case of a reaction at x and t , matters become a little more complicated. Before the reaction, one has:

$$P_1, p_2, \text{ at } x \text{ at } t_1 \quad ((2a)) \quad \text{and after the reaction} \quad p_3, p_4 \text{ at } x \text{ at } t_2 \quad ((2b))$$

In other words, t must change for an interaction to occur in Newtonian mechanics (e.g. impulse $\int dt F$), but x does not. If one uses $P(p, x)$ without specifying time, how does one show that p_3+p_4 exist at a later time and p_1+p_2 at an earlier? We argue that one must use the time inherent in p which is guaranteed to be associated with velocity, for light and for a particle with rest mass. Thus, we suggest using $-p_3-p_4$ for the later time. This is like a time reversed view point. For conservation of momentum, using ((1b)) on e has for an interaction:

$$\exp(C (-p_3-p_4)) \exp(C (p_1+p_2)) \quad ((3))$$

The problem is that this probability, which ignores x , is not 0 if p_3+p_4 (vectors) does not equal p_1+p_2 .

Newtonian mechanics insists that momentum be conserved at any given x for an interaction at that x . In the probability scenario one must have $P(p_1)P(p_2)=P(p_1+p_2)$ and so it seems difficult to have 0 probability for the case of no momentum conservation.

Mathematically, a two-body collision may exist at any x point and if one consider this, one may formally write the looser statement:

$$\text{Sum over } x \ P(-p_3-p_4, x) P(p_1+p_2, x) = 0 \quad ((4))$$

((4)) indicates that one cannot remove x from probability which is a different idea from Newtonian mechanics. ((4)) also shows that the conservation of momentum in the probability view only appears if one sums (integrates) over all space. Thus, one must have two orthogonal functions in x , $P(p_1,x)P(p_2,x) = P(p_1+p_2,x)$. This may be achieved using:

$$P(p,x) = \exp(ipx) \quad ((5))$$

((5)), however, is an unusual probability in that it is complex and depends on x . The combination of these two features, however, leads to a constant modulus at each x which is good. A fundamental point is that the momentum conserving probability ((5)) must contain two variables, p and x , and so is immediately associated with a continuity of $\exp(ipx)$ s at a symmetry breaking x_0 point as well as continuity of $p \exp(ipx)$ at x_0 .

We note that for ((4)), one only considers p_1, p_2 and $-p_3, -p_4$ at x at some common time. One does not know what p_1, p_2, p_3, p_4 were doing before this time. In Newtonian mechanics, they could have been accelerating.

If one considers $\exp(ipx)$ by itself, one states that one may p at any x . The same p is at any x and so this should coincide with a particle with constant momentum p . The fact that there is a repeating cycle in x , (wavelength = \hbar/p), however, is unusual and non-Newtonian. It seems that $\exp(ipx)$ gives a probability for a p appearing at x , but from the above arguments $\exp(-ipx)$ could, under certain circumstances, represent time reversed motion, as well as simply momentum to the left. Both of these interpretations may be useful because as noted above, one may have p_3+p_4 and p_1+p_2 at the same x at different times.

We try to consider a physical situation which justifies $\exp(ipx)$, namely one dimensional reflection-refraction of a photon. An interesting feature of ((5)) is that it is a continuous function, but as a probability should be used to compute averages. In particular, at least $p \exp(ipx)$ should be relevant if one considers a probability view. Now, a particle may suffer a Newtonian impulse at x_0 , so p may change. One would expect probability $\exp(ipx)$ to be continuous at x_0 as well as the average density $p \exp(ipx)$, but these two conditions cannot hold i.e.

$$A \exp(ipx_0) = A \exp(-ip_2 x_0) \quad ((6a)) \quad \text{and} \quad A p \exp(ipx_0) = A p_2 \exp(ip_2 x_0) \quad ((6b))$$

Given that $p_2 > p_1$, it seems that the weight of $\exp(ip_2 x_0)$ cannot be the same as that of $\exp(ipx_0)$.

Given that one considers probabilities in space and that one may consider time reversed probabilities at the same x as well, using this math one may actually modulate weights such as

A. A time reversed probability, however, must ultimately correspond to a physical result at a later time.

If one considers that energy remains constant for a photon, then $E=pc$ and a change in momentum is accompanied by a change in c . For a photon moving to the right with p , there is also a $-p$ solution with the same energy. Given that x -symmetry is broken at x_0 (which may be anywhere), then one may combine $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$ to the left of x_0 and apply continuity of probability and p multiplied by probability. In a non-probabilistic picture, $-p$ must occur at a later time and so should p^2 . The $-p$ is the time reversed solution of p . $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$ exist on the LHS side of x_0 , but it is like one is the movie time reverse of the other. In other words, the $\exp(ipx)$ approach allows one to consider probability and time reversed probability (i.e. probability at a different time) at the same x . This allows one to modulate coefficients of $\exp(ipx)$.

Given that one has two possibilities at a later time e.g. p and then $-p$, p^2 and that one deals with probabilities, one would expect non- x interfering probabilities for these two events. As discussed in previous notes this is exactly what happens through the difference of squares provided by probability and p * probability continuity if one adds in $\exp(-ipx)$.

If one writes:

$$A\exp(ipx) + B\exp(-ipx) = C\exp(ip^2x) \quad ((7a)) \text{ and } A\exp(ipx) - B\exp(-ipx) = C\exp(ip^2x) \quad ((7b))$$

and uses $x_0=0$ and multiplies ((7a)) by ((7b)), then one has: $AAp - pBB = CCp^2$ ((8))

We note the $B\exp(-ipx)$ is like a time reversed probability and that B may even be negative (as it is for the case of $n_1 < n_2$, where n_i is the index of refraction). Here one is simply dealing with probabilities in x which may or may not exist at the same time as seen above. (This is somewhat akin to steady fluxes which may be why AA , BB and CC are physically fluxes as is seen later.) If one considered an $\exp(-ip^2x)$, it seems there would be no physical reason to have such a flow from the right to left physically. In other words, an event at a later time, namely $\exp(-ipx)$ may be considered as existing as probability in space (which does not contain time in the form of ((7a)) ((7b))) to create continuity at x_0 . This is like saying that given classically a flux in one direction and probabilities for it to do something else, a future event existing in the same x space as the initial probability can diminish it. This accounts for some loss of probability of the initial beam which is expected. This situation also occurs in scattering problems for which there is an initial flux and only some probability for scattering. Back scattering interferes with the incident probability (even though both occur at different times) to account for a loss in probability of the incident beam. Thus, the $\exp(ipx)$ approach deals with probabilities in space even if they occur at different times.

Now x no longer appears, but $-p$ is on the LHS and represents time reversed motion. Bringing it to the RHS yields a separation in time between the LHS and RHS and a classical probability equation:

Incident Probability = Reflected Probability + Refracted Probability ((9)) or

$$AA p = BB p + CC p^2 \quad ((10))$$

Given that $E=pc$, $p = E/c$ and E is the same, so AA , BB , CC must be fluxes i.e. number of particles * velocity.

((9)) is a probability in time equation whereas ((7a)) and ((7b)) are probability and $p * \text{probability}$ in space and p equations. Thus, they lead to two equations, one associated with probability in space and one with average p in space. Given that one considers two actions- reflection and refraction- one requires two probability type balance equations and these are given by separate x ($\exp(ipx)$ probability continuity) and p ($p * \exp(ipx)$ balance).

Classically, the incident photon exists at time t_1 and the reflected or refracted, at $t_2 > t_1$. Nevertheless, there are x and p probability considerations associated with these and the orthogonality of $\exp(-i(p_3+p_4)x)$ and $\exp(i(p_1+p_2)x)$ shows that there are momentum conservation issues in space even if events occur at different times. In other words, even if the incident photon is gone, there are still conservation of momentum ramifications due to the momentum it had.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we try to consider a probabilistic approach which yields conservation of momentum. We note that $P(p_1)P(p_2) = P(p_1+p_2)$, where p_1, p_2 are vectors. This leads to a power law with p_1 in the power for one dimension. If one has an interaction, i.e. $p_1+p_2 = p_3+p_4$, then one should have $P(p_1+p_2)$ and $P(p_3+p_4)$, but this does not become zero if p_1+p_2 is not equal to p_3+p_4 . As written, we have not included x , so one may consider adding x to try to find orthogonality. We argued that p_1+p_2 and p_3+p_4 exist at the same x , but at different times. To distinguish, we suggest using the time reversed form: $-p_3-p_4$.

Formally, we also considered the interaction at only one x point, but it may occur at any, so one should sum (i.e. integrate) over x , and this suggests orthogonal functions. Thus, instead of using $\exp(\text{constant } p)$, one may use $\exp(ipx)$ for probability, where it is actually the i which makes the function periodic (so it does not grow or shrink indefinitely).

We extend these ideas to one dimensional reflection-refraction and argue that given $\exp(ipx)$, it applies to probability in x which should be continuous at x and also to an average p density, i.e. $p \exp(ipx)$. Thus, there are two inherent continuities because it was not possible to simply create a probability using p alone. In other words, there will be two continuity equations using $\exp(ipx)$, one for $\exp(ipx)$ and one for $p \exp(ipx)$.

This seems to be useful for the one dimensional reflection-refraction of photons problem. Even though events occur at different times, momentum conservation ramifications allow one to consider momentum at different times at the same x and automatically yield two equations. Given that $1 = \text{probability to reflect} + \text{probability to refract}$, there are two unknowns and one equation and the p - x probability approach allows for this to be solved, whereas the time equation (one equation) does not. The p - x approach is considered because it is a way of

ensuring momentum conservation which must hold. Thus, it has a physical basis, and is not a math trick.